

From a different point of view to near-rings: Soft zero-symmetric and constant parts of soft near-rings with applications

Akın Osman ATAGÜN¹ and Aslihan SEZGİN^{2*}

¹Department of Mathematics, Kırşehir Ahi Evran University,
Kırşehir, Turkey. ORCID iD: [0000-0002-2131-9980](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2131-9980)

²Department of Mathematics and Science Education, Amasya University,
Amasya City, Turkey. ORCID iD: [0000-0002-1519-7294](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1519-7294)

Received: 10 Feb 2024

Accepted: 23 Mar 2024

Published Online: 01 Jul 2024

Abstract: In this study, we describe soft parts, named soft 0-symmetric and soft constant parts, of soft intersection near-rings and soft union near-rings, and obtain their fundamental features. We explore the relations between the parts of near-rings and soft parts of soft intersection near-rings and soft union near-rings, and we give some applications of these parts to soft sets. Additionally, soft intersection (union) product of soft intersection (union) near-ring are introduced and applied on soft parts of soft intersection near-rings and soft union near-rings, respectively.

Key words: Soft set, soft intersection near-ring, soft union near-ring, soft zero symmetric part, soft constant part

1. Introduction

Soft set theory was introduced by Molodtsov [1] as a way to model vagueness and uncertainty. Since then, work on the theory has advanced quickly and found a wide range of applications, including the mean of algebraic structures as in [2–23], as well as the structures and operations of soft sets as in [28–46]. Additionally, the theory of soft sets keeps growing and diversifying tremendously in the mean of soft decision making, as demonstrated by the papers listed below [24–27, 47–49, 51].

Sezgin et al. [52] defined a new concept, soft intersection near-ring, by utilizing soft sets and the intersection operation of sets. This concept combines near-ring theory, set theory, and soft set theory, making it highly useful for obtaining results in the mean of near-ring structure. They provide several applications of soft int near-rings to near-ring theory based on the definition. Additionally, Sezgin et al. [53] established a new concept, soft union near-ring, and provided some applications of soft uni near-rings to near-ring theory by utilizing soft sets and the intersection operation of sets.

Manikantan et al. [50] introduced the concepts of soft zero-symmetric near-ring, soft constant near-ring, soft near-field and soft Q- simple near-ring over a near-ring and investigated the properties of these notions with illustrative example in a different manner. In this paper, we try to convey the concept of 0-symmetric and constant parts of a near-ring to soft intersection near-rings and soft union near-rings as soft 0-symmetric and soft constant parts, and derive their basic properties. We give some applications of these soft parts to soft sets and study relations between the parts of near-rings and soft parts of soft int near-rings and soft union near-rings. Finally, we define soft int (uni) product of soft intersection (union) near-ring and give the applications of them on soft parts of soft intersection near-rings and soft union near-rings, respectively. In a near-ring structure,

0-symmetric and constant parts are of great importance for chracterization of the near-ring; so constructing the soft 0-symmetric part and soft constant part help the soft near-ring theory to improve.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we recall some basic notions relevant to near-rings and soft sets. By a *near-ring*, we shall mean an algebraic system $(N, +, \cdot)$, where

N1) $(N, +)$ forms a group (not necessarily abelian)

N2) (N, \cdot) forms a semi-group and

N3) $(a + b)c = ac + bc$ for all $a, b, c \in N$ (i.e. we study on right near-rings.)

Throughout this paper, N will always denote a right near-ring with zero element 0. The subset $\{n \in N : n0 = 0\}$ of N , is called a zero-symmetric part of N and denoted by N_0 and the subset $\{n \in N : n0 = n\}$ of N , is called a constant part of N and denoted by N_c . For all undefined concepts and notions regarding near-rings and semi-nearring, we refer to [54, 55]. From now on, U refers to an initial universe, E is a set of parameters, $P(U)$ is the power set of U and $A, B, C \subseteq E$.

Definition 2.1. [1, 48] A soft set ξ_A over U is a set defined by

$$\xi_A : E \rightarrow P(U) \text{ such that } \xi_A(x) = \emptyset \text{ if } x \notin A.$$

Here, ξ_A is also called *approximate function*. A soft set over U can be represented by the set of ordered pairs

$$\xi_A = \{(x, \xi_A(x)) : x \in E, \xi_A(x) \in P(U)\}.$$

It is clear to see that a soft set is a parametrized family of subsets of the set U . It is worth noting that the sets $\xi_A(x)$ may be arbitrary. Some of them may be empty, some may have nonempty intersection. We refer to [1, 28, 48] for further details.

Definition 2.2. [48] Let ξ_A and ξ_B be soft sets over U . Then, *union* of ξ_A and ξ_B , denoted by $\xi_A \widetilde{\cup} \xi_B$, is defined as $\xi_A \widetilde{\cup} \xi_B = \xi_{A \widetilde{\cup} B}$, where $\xi_{A \widetilde{\cup} B}(x) = \xi_A(x) \cup \xi_B(x)$ for all $x \in E$.

Intersection of ξ_A and ξ_B , denoted by $\xi_A \widetilde{\cap} \xi_B$, is defined as $\xi_A \widetilde{\cap} \xi_B = f_{A \widetilde{\cap} B}$, where $f_{A \widetilde{\cap} B}(x) = \xi_A(x) \cap \xi_B(x)$ for all $x \in E$.

Definition 2.3. [48] Let ξ_A and ξ_B be soft sets over U . Then, *\vee -product* of ξ_A and ξ_B , denoted by $\xi_A \vee \xi_B$, is defined as $\xi_A \vee \xi_B = \xi_{A \vee B}$, where $\xi_{A \vee B}(x, y) = \xi_A(x) \cup \xi_B(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in E \times E$.

\wedge -product of ξ_A and ξ_B , denoted by $\xi_A \wedge \xi_B$, is defined as $\xi_A \wedge \xi_B = f_{A \wedge B}$, where $\xi_{A \wedge B}(x, y) = \xi_A(x) \cap \xi_B(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in E \times E$.

Definition 2.4. [29] Let ξ_A and ξ_B be soft sets over U . Then, *restricted union* of ξ_A and ξ_B , denoted by $\xi_A \cup_{\mathcal{R}} \xi_B$, is defined defined as $\xi_A \cup_{\mathcal{R}} \xi_B = \xi_{A \cup_{\mathcal{R}} B}$, where $\xi_{A \cup_{\mathcal{R}} B}(x) = \xi_A(x) \cup \xi_B(x)$ for all $x \in A \cap B \neq \emptyset$.

Restricted intersection of ξ_A and ξ_B , denoted by $\xi_A \cap_{\mathcal{R}} \xi_B$, is defined as $\xi_A \cap_{\mathcal{R}} \xi_B = f_{A \cap_{\mathcal{R}} B}$, where $\xi_{A \cap_{\mathcal{R}} B}(x) = \xi_A(x) \cap \xi_B(x)$ for all $x \in A \cap B \neq \emptyset$.

Definition 2.5. ([52]) Let N be a near-ring and ξ_N be a soft set over U . Then, ξ_N is called *soft int near-ring* over U if

- i) $\xi_N(x + y) \supseteq \xi_N(x) \cap \xi_N(y)$
- ii) $\xi_N(-x) = \xi_N(x)$
- iii) $\xi_N(xy) \supseteq \xi_N(x) \cap \xi_N(y)$

for all $x, y \in N$.

From now on, soft int near-ring is designated by SIN .

Proposition 2.1. [52] Let ξ_N be a SIN over U . Then, $\xi_N(0) \supseteq \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in N$.

Theorem 2.1. [52] If ξ_N and ξ_M are SIN s over U , then so is $\xi_N \wedge \xi_M$ over U .

Definition 2.6. [52] Let ξ_N, g_M be SIN s over U . Then, the *product of SIN s* ξ_N and g_M is defined as $\xi_N \times g_M = h_{N \times M}$, where $h_{N \times M}(x, y) = \xi_N(x) \times g_M(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in N \times M$.

Theorem 2.2. [52] If ξ_N and g_M are SIN s over U , then so is $\xi_N \times g_M$ over $U \times U$.

Theorem 2.3. [52] If ξ_N and h_N are two SIN s over U , then so is $\xi_N \widetilde{\cap} h_N$ over U .

Definition 2.7. [53] Let N be a near-ring and ξ_N be a soft set over U . Then, ξ_N is called a *soft uni near-ring* over U if it satisfies the following properties:

- i) $\xi_N(x + y) \subseteq \xi_N(x) \cup \xi_N(y)$,
- ii) $\xi_N(-x) = \xi_N(x)$,
- iii) $\xi_N(xy) \subseteq \xi_N(x) \cup \xi_N(y)$

for all $x, y \in N$.

From now on, soft uni near-ring is designated by SUN and near-ring by NR .

Proposition 2.2. [53] Let ξ_N be a SUN over U . Then, $\xi_N(0) \subseteq \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in N$.

Theorem 2.4. [53] If ξ_N and ξ_M are SUN s over U , then so is $\xi_N \vee \xi_M$ over U .

Theorem 2.5. [53] If ξ_N and h_N are two SUN s over U , then so is $\xi_N \widetilde{\cup} h_N$ over U .

3. Soft parts of soft int near-rings

Now, we define soft zero-symmetric and soft constant parts of SIN s.

Definition 3.1. Let ξ_N be a SIN over U and $M \subseteq N$. Let ξ_M be the restricted function of f to M , i.e. for all $x \in M$ $\xi_M(x) = \xi_N(x)$. If M is a maximal subset of N such that

- i) For all $m \in M$, $\xi_M(m0) = \xi_M(0)$, then the soft set ξ_M is called the soft zero-symmetric part of ξ_N and denoted by $(F_N)_0$.

Table 1. Addition and Multiplication Tables of N

$+$	0	a	b	c	\cdot	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	c	b	a	a	a	a	a
b	b	c	0	a	b	0	0	b	0
c	c	b	a	0	c	a	a	c	a

ii) For all $m \in M$, $\xi_M(m0) = \xi_M(m)$, then the soft set ξ_M is called the soft constant part of ξ_N and denoted by $(\xi_N)_c$.

Example 3.1. Let the NR $(N, +, \cdot)$ be defined on the Klein's four group $N = \{0, a, b, c\}$ as following [54].

Assume that N is the set of parameters and $U = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} x & x \\ y & y \end{bmatrix} \mid x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_4 \right\}$, 2×2 matrices with \mathbb{Z}_4 terms, is the universal set. We construct a soft set ξ_N over U by

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_N(0) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 3 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \\ \xi_N(a) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 3 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \\ \xi_N(b) &= \xi_N(c) = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, one can easily show that ξ_N is a SIN over U . Since $M = \{0, b\}$ is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_M(m0) = \xi_M(0)$ for all $m \in M$, then $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Similarly, since $K = \{0, a\}$ is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_K(k0) = \xi_K(k)$ for all $k \in K$, then $(\xi_N)_c = \xi_K$.

If $N = N_0$ or $N = N_c$, the soft zero-symmetric part of ξ_N or soft constant part of ξ_N are easily obtained by following theorem:

Theorem 3.1. Let ξ_N be a SIN over U .

i) If $N = N_0$, then $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_N$.

ii) If $N = N_c$, then $(\xi_N)_c = \xi_N$.

Proof. **i)** If $N = N_0$, then $n0 = 0$ for all $n \in N$. Hence $\xi_N(n0) = \xi_N(0)$ for all $n \in N$. Therefore $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_N$.

ii) If $N = N_c$, then $n0 = n$ for all $n \in N$. Hence $\xi_N(n0) = \xi_N(n)$ for all $n \in N$. Therefore $(\xi_N)_c = \xi_N$. \square

The converse of Theorem 3.1 doesn't hold, in general. We have the following example:

Example 3.2. Let the NR $(N, +, \cdot)$ be defined on the Klein's four group $N = \{0, a, b, c\}$ as in Table 2. Assume that N is the set of parameters and $U = \mathbb{Z}_5$ is the universal set. We construct a soft set ξ_N over U by $\xi_N(0) = \xi_N(a) = \mathbb{Z}_5$, $\xi_N(b) = \xi_N(c) = \{0, 1, 2\}$. The one can easily show that ξ_N is a SIN over U . Since $\xi_N(a0) = \xi_N(a) = \xi_N(0)$, $\xi_N(b0) = \xi_N(0)$ and $\xi_N(c0) = \xi_N(a) = \xi_N(0)$, then $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_N$, but $a0 \neq 0$, i.e. N

Table 2. Addition and Multiplication Tables of N

+	0	a	b	c	.	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	c	b	a	a	a	a	a
b	b	c	0	a	b	0	0	b	b
c	c	b	a	0	c	a	a	c	c

is not a zero-symmetric NR.

If we define another soft set ζ_N over U by $\zeta_N(0) = \zeta_N(a) = \zeta_N(b) = \zeta_N(c) = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, then ζ_N is a SIN over U . Since $\zeta_N(n0) = \zeta_N(n)$ for all $n \in N$, $(\zeta_N)_c = \zeta_N$. But $b0 = 0 \neq b$, i.e. N is not a constant NR.

Theorem 3.2. Let N and M be NRs and let ξ_N and ζ_M be SINs over U . Then,

- i) $(\xi_N)_0 \wedge (\zeta_M)_0 = (\xi_N \wedge \zeta_M)_0$
- ii) $(\xi_N)_c \wedge (\zeta_M)_c = (\xi_N \wedge \zeta_M)_c$

Proof. **i)** By Theorem 2.1, $\xi_N \wedge \zeta_M$ is a SIN over U . Assume that $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_K$ and $(\zeta_M)_0 = \zeta_L$. Then K is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_K(x) = \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in K$ and L is a maximal subset of M such that $\zeta_L(x) = \zeta_M(x)$ for all $x \in L$. By Definition 2.3, let $\xi_K \wedge \zeta_L = t_{K \wedge L}$, where $t_{K \wedge L}(x, y) = \xi_K(x) \cap \zeta_L(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in K \times L$. Let $(k, l) \in K \times L$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\xi_K \wedge \zeta_L)((k, l).(0, 0)) &= t_{K \wedge L}(k0, l0) \\
 &= \xi_K(k0) \cap \zeta_L(l0) \\
 &= \xi_K(0) \cap \zeta_L(0) \\
 &= t_{K \wedge L}(0, 0)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\xi_K \wedge \zeta_L = (\xi_N)_0 \wedge (\zeta_M)_0 = (\xi_N \wedge \zeta_M)_0$. The rest of the proof can be obtained similarly. \square

Theorem 3.3. Let N and M be NRs and let ξ_N and ζ_M be SINs over U . Then,

- i) $(\xi_N)_0 \times (\zeta_M)_0 = (\xi_N \times \zeta_M)_0$
- ii) $(\xi_N)_c \times (\zeta_M)_c = (\xi_N \times \zeta_M)_c$

Proof. **i)** By Theorem 2.2, $\xi_N \times \zeta_M$ is a SIN over $U \times U$. Assume that $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_K$ and $(\zeta_M)_0 = \zeta_L$. Then, K is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_K(x) = \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in K$ and L is a maximal subset of M such that $\zeta_L(x) = \zeta_M(x)$ for all $x \in L$. By Definition 2.6, let $\xi_K \times \zeta_L = t_{K \times L}$, where $t_{K \times L}(x, y) = \xi_K(x) \times \zeta_L(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in K \times L$. Let $(k, l) \in K \times L$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\xi_K \times \zeta_L)((k, l).(0, 0)) &= t_{K \times L}(k0, l0) \\
 &= \xi_K(k0) \times \zeta_L(l0) \\
 &= \xi_K(0) \times \zeta_L(0) \\
 &= t_{K \times L}(0, 0)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\xi_K \times \zeta_L = (\xi_N)_0 \times (\zeta_M)_0 = (\xi_N \times \zeta_M)_0$. The rest of the proof can be obtained similarly. \square

Theorem 3.4. *Let ξ_N and ζ_N be SINs over U . Then,*

- i) $(\xi_N)_0 \tilde{\cap} (\zeta_N)_0 = (\xi_N \tilde{\cap} \zeta_N)_0$
- ii) $(\xi_N)_c \tilde{\cap} (\zeta_N)_c = (\xi_N \tilde{\cap} \zeta_N)_c$

Proof. **i)** By Theorem 2.3, $\xi_N \tilde{\cap} \zeta_N$ is a SIN over U . Assume that $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_K$ and $(\zeta_N)_0 = \zeta_L$. Then, K is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_K(x) = \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in K$ and L is a maximal subset of N such that $\zeta_L(x) = \zeta_N(x)$ for all $x \in L$. By Definition 2.2, let $\xi_K \tilde{\cap} \zeta_L = t_{K \tilde{\cap} L}$, where $t_{K \tilde{\cap} L}(x) = \xi_K(x) \cap \zeta_L(x)$ for all $x \in N$. Let $x \in N$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_K \tilde{\cap} \zeta_L)(x_0) &= t_{K \tilde{\cap} L}(x_0) \\ &= \xi_K(x_0) \cap \zeta_L(x_0) \\ &= \xi_K(0) \cap \zeta_L(0) \\ &= t_{K \tilde{\cap} L}(0) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\xi_K \tilde{\cap} \zeta_L = (\xi_N)_0 \tilde{\cap} (\zeta_N)_0 = (\xi_N \tilde{\cap} \zeta_N)_0$. The rest of the proof can be obtained similarly. \square

Corollary 3.1. *Let ξ_N and ζ_N be SINs over U . Then,*

- i) $(\xi_N)_0 \cap (\zeta_N)_0 = (\xi_N \cap \zeta_N)_0$
- ii) $(\xi_N)_c \cap (\zeta_N)_c = (\xi_N \cap \zeta_N)_c$

Proof. The proof is similar to proof of Theorem 3.4, hence omitted. \square

4. Soft parts of soft uni near-rings

Now, we define soft zero-symmetric and soft constant parts of SUNs.

Definition 4.1. Let ξ_N be a SUN over U and $M \subseteq N$. Let ξ_M be the restricted function of f to M , i.e. for all $x \in M$ $\xi_M(x) = \xi_N(x)$. If M is a maximal subset of N such that

- i) For all $m \in M$, $\xi_M(m_0) = \xi_M(0)$, then the soft set ξ_M is called the soft zero-symmetric part of ξ_N and denoted by $(\xi_N)_0$.
- ii) For all $m \in M$, $\xi_M(m_0) = \xi_M(m)$, then the soft set ξ_M is called the soft constant part of ξ_N and denoted by $(\xi_N)_c$.

Example 4.1. Consider the additive group $(\mathbb{Z}_6, +)$. Under a multiplication given in the Table 3, $N = (\mathbb{Z}_6, +, \cdot)$ is a (right) NR [56].

Let $N = \mathbb{Z}_6$ be the set of parameters and $U = \mathbb{Z}^+$ be the universal set. We define a soft set ξ_N over U by

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_N(0) &= \{2, 4\}, \\ \xi_N(1) &= \xi_N(5) = \{2, 4, 6, 8, 10\}, \\ \xi_N(3) &= \{2, 4, 8, 10\}, \\ \xi_N(2) &= \xi_N(4) = \{2, 4, 6, 10\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, ξ_N is a SUN over U . Since $M = \{0, 2, 4\}$ is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_M(m_0) = \xi_M(0)$ for all $m \in M$, then $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Similarly, since $K = \{0, 3\}$ is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_K(k_0) = \xi_K(k)$ for all $k \in K$, then $(\xi_N)_c = \xi_K$.

Table 3. Multiplication Table of N

.	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	3	1	5	3	1	5
2	0	2	4	0	2	4
3	3	3	3	3	3	3
4	0	4	2	0	4	2
5	3	5	1	3	5	1

Theorem 4.1. Let ξ_N be a SUN over U .

i) If $N = N_0$, then $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_N$.

ii) If $N = N_c$, then $(\xi_N)_c = \xi_N$.

Proof. Similar to proof of Theorem 3.1, hence omitted. \square

The converse of Theorem 4.1 doesn't hold, in general. We have the following example:

Example 4.2. Let the NR $N = (Z_6, +, \cdot)$ be in Example 4.1. Assume that N is the set of parameters and $U = Z$, is the universal set. If we define a soft set F_N over U by $\xi_N(0) = \xi_N(1) = \xi_N(2) = \xi_N(3) = \xi_N(4) = \xi_N(5) = Z$, then ξ_N is a SUN over U and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_N$, but $3 \cdot 0 \neq 0$, i.e. N is not a zero-symmetric NR. If we define another soft set ζ_N over U by $\zeta_N(0) = \zeta_N(2) = \zeta_N(4) = \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $\zeta_N(1) = \zeta_N(3) = \zeta_N(5) = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, then ζ_N is a SUN over U . Since $\zeta_N(00) = \zeta_N(0)$, $\zeta_N(10) = \zeta_N(3) = \zeta_N(1)$, $\zeta_N(20) = \zeta_N(0) = \zeta_N(2)$, $\zeta_N(30) = \zeta_N(3)$, $\zeta_N(40) = \zeta_N(0) = \zeta_N(4)$ and $\zeta_N(50) = \zeta_N(3) = \zeta_N(5)$, then $(\zeta_N)_c = \zeta_N$. But $1 \cdot 0 = 3 \neq 1$, i.e. N is not a constant NR.

Theorem 4.2. Let N and M be NRs and let ξ_N and g_M be SUNs over U . Then,

i) $(\xi_N)_0 \vee (g_M)_0 = (\xi_N \vee g_M)_0$

ii) $(\xi_N)_c \vee (g_M)_c = (\xi_N \vee g_M)_c$

Proof. **i)** By Theorem 2.4, $\xi_N \vee g_M$ is a SUN over U . Assume that $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_K$ and $(g_M)_0 = \zeta_L$. Then, K is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_K(x) = \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in K$ and L is a maximal subset of M such that $\zeta_L(x) = g_M(x)$ for all $x \in L$. By Definition 2.3, let $\xi_K \vee \zeta_L = t_{K \vee L}$, where $t_{K \vee L}(x, y) = \xi_K(x) \cup \zeta_L(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in K \times L$. Let $(k, l) \in K \times L$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\xi_K \vee \zeta_L)((k, l) \cdot (0, 0)) &= t_{K \vee L}(k0, l0) \\
 &= \xi_K(k0) \cup \zeta_L(l0) \\
 &= \xi_K(0) \cup \zeta_L(0) \\
 &= t_{K \vee L}(0, 0)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\xi_K \vee \zeta_L = (\xi_N)_0 \vee (g_M)_0 = (\xi_N \vee g_M)_0$. The rest of the proof can be obtained similarly. \square

Theorem 4.3. Let ξ_N and ζ_N be SUNs over U . Then,

$$i) (\xi_N)_0 \tilde{\cup} (\zeta_N)_0 = (\xi_N \tilde{\cup} \zeta_N)_0$$

$$ii) (\xi_N)_c \tilde{\cup} (\zeta_N)_c = (\xi_N \tilde{\cup} \zeta_N)_c$$

Proof. **i)** By Theorem 2.5, $\xi_N \tilde{\cup} \zeta_N$ is a *SIN* over U . Assume that $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_K$ and $(\zeta_N)_0 = \zeta_L$. Then, K is a maximal subset of N such that $\xi_K(x) = \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in K$ and L is a maximal subset of N such that $\zeta_L(x) = \zeta_N(x)$ for all $x \in L$. By Definition 2.2, let $\xi_K \tilde{\cup} \zeta_L = t_{K \tilde{\cup} L}$, where $t_{K \tilde{\cup} L}(x) = \xi_K(x) \cup \zeta_L(x)$ for all $x \in N$. Let $x \in N$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_K \tilde{\cup} \zeta_L)(x) &= t_{K \tilde{\cup} L}(x) \\ &= \xi_K(x) \cup \zeta_L(x) \\ &= \xi_K(0) \cup \zeta_L(0) \\ &= f_{K \tilde{\cup} L}(0) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\xi_K \tilde{\cup} \zeta_L = (\xi_N)_0 \tilde{\cup} (\zeta_N)_0 = (\xi_N \tilde{\cup} \zeta_N)_0$. The rest of the proof can be obtained similarly. \square

Corollary 4.1. *Let ξ_N and ζ_N be SUNs over U . Then,*

$$i) (\xi_N)_0 \cup_{\mathcal{R}} (\zeta_N)_0 = (\xi_N \cup_{\mathcal{R}} \zeta_N)_0$$

$$ii) (\xi_N)_c \cup_{\mathcal{R}} (\zeta_N)_c = (\xi_N \cup_{\mathcal{R}} \zeta_N)_c$$

Proof. The proof is similar to proof of Theorem 4.3. \square

5. Soft int-product applied on soft parts of SINs

Definition 5.1. Let N be a *NR* and ξ_N and ζ_N be soft sets over the common universe U . Then, *soft int-product* $\xi_N \circ \zeta_N$ is defined by

$$(\xi_N \circ \zeta_N)(x) = \begin{cases} \bigcup_{x=yz} \{\xi_N(y) \cap \zeta_N(z)\}, & \text{if } \exists y, z \in N \text{ such that } x = yz, \\ \emptyset, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for all $x \in N$. It is obvious that if N is a *NR* with identity, then the second condition does not exist.

Let ξ_N and ζ_N be soft sets over U . If $\xi_N(x) \subset \zeta_N(x)$ for all $x \in N$, then we denote it by

$$\xi_N \subset \zeta_N.$$

It is well-known that $N_0 N_0 \subseteq N_0$. Similarly, we have the following theorem:

Theorem 5.1. *Let ξ_N be a SIN and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Then,*

$$\xi_M \circ \xi_M \subset \xi_M.$$

Proof. Let $m \in M$. If $(\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(m) = \emptyset$, then it is obvious that

$$\xi_M \circ \xi_M(m) \subseteq \xi_M(m),$$

for all $m \in M$. Thus,

$$\xi_M \circ \xi_M \subset \xi_M.$$

Otherwise, there exist elements $x, y \in M$ such that $m = xy$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(m) &= \bigcup_{m=xy} \{\xi_M(x) \cap \xi_M(y)\} \\
 &\subseteq \bigcup_{m=xy} \xi_M(xy) \\
 &= \bigcup \xi_M(m) \\
 &= \xi_M(m)
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\xi_M \circ \xi_M \subset \xi_M.$$

Here, note that since ξ_N is a *SIN*, $\xi_N(xy) \supseteq \xi_N(x) \cap \xi_N(y)$ for all $x \in N$. And, since ξ_M is the restricted function of f to M , then $\xi_M(xy) \supseteq \xi_M(x) \cap \xi_M(y)$. That is, ξ_M is a *SIN*, too. \square

Note that the converse of Theorem 5.1, that is $\xi_M \subset \xi_M \circ \xi_M$, does not hold as seen in the following example.

Example 5.1. [52] Let $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be the (right) NR due to [54] (Near-rings of low order (D-10)) defined by the following tables:

$+$	0	1	2	3	\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	2	3	0	1	0	1	2	1
2	2	3	0	1	2	0	2	0	2
3	3	0	1	2	3	0	3	2	3

Assume that N is the set of parameters and $U = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} x & x \\ y & y \end{bmatrix} \mid x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_4 \right\}$, 2×2 matrices with \mathbb{Z}_4 terms, is the universal set. We define a soft set ξ_N over U by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \xi_N(0) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 3 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \\
 \xi_N(1) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \\
 \xi_N(2) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \\
 \xi_N(3) &= \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, one can easily show that the soft set ξ_N is a *SIN* over U . Since N is a zero-symmetric NR, then $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_N$ by Theorem 3.1. It is seen that

$$\xi_N(2) = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}$$

and

$$(\xi_N \circ \xi_N)(2) = \left\{ \left[\begin{array}{cc} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{cc} 3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 \end{array} \right] \right\}.$$

Therefore, $\xi_N \not\subset \xi_N \circ \xi_N$.

As is seen, $\xi_M \circ \xi_M$ needs not be equal to ξ_M , however we have the following :

Theorem 5.2. *Let ξ_N be a SIN and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Then,*

$$(\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(0) = \xi_M(0).$$

Proof. $(\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(0) \subseteq \xi_M(0)$ is obvious by Theorem 5.1. Thus, we need to show that

$$(\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(0) \supseteq \xi_M(0).$$

Note that

$$(\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(0) \neq \emptyset, \text{ since } 0 = 0 \cdot 0.$$

So, let $x, y \in M$ such that $0 = xy$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(0) &= \bigcup_{0=xy} \{\xi_M(x) \cap \xi_M(y)\} \\ &\supseteq \xi_M(0) \cap \xi_M(0) \text{ (since } 0 = 0 \cdot 0) \\ &= \xi_M(0) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the proof is completed. □

It is known that if ξ_N is a SIN, then $\xi_N(0) \supseteq \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in N$. Moreover, we have the following:

Theorem 5.3. *Let $N = N_0$, ξ_N be a SIN and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Then,*

$$(\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(0) \subsetneq \xi_M(x)$$

for all $x \in M$.

Proof. Let $x, y \in M$ such that $0 = xy$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_M \circ \xi_M)(0) &= \bigcup_{0=xy} \{\xi_M(x) \cap \xi_M(y)\} \\ &\supseteq \xi_M(x) \cap \xi_M(0) \text{ (since } N = N_0, 0 = x0) \\ &\supseteq \xi_M(x) \cap \xi_M(x) \text{ (by Lemma 2.1)} \\ &= \xi_M(x) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the proof is completed. □

It is known that $N_c N_c \subseteq N_c$. However, we have the following theorem:

Theorem 5.4. *Let $N = N_c$, ξ_N be a SIN and $(\xi_N)_c = \xi_C$. Then,*

$$\xi_C \circ \xi_C = \xi_C.$$

Proof. Here, first note that

$$(\xi_C \circ \xi_C) \neq \emptyset$$

since $N = N_c$, for all $c \in N$, $c = c \cdot 0$. So, let $x, y \in C$ such that $c = xy$. It follows that,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_C \circ \xi_C)(c) &= \bigcup_{c=xy} \{\xi_C(x) \cap \xi_C(y)\} \\ &\subseteq \bigcup_{c=xy} \xi_C(xy) \quad (\text{since } \xi_C \text{ is a soft int near - ring}) \\ &= \bigcup \xi_C(c) \\ &= \xi_C(c) \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\xi_C \circ \xi_C \subset \xi_C.$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_C \circ \xi_C)(c) &= \bigcup_{c=xy} \{f_C(x) \cap f_C(y)\} \\ &\supseteq f_C(c) \cap f_C(0) \quad (\text{since } N = N_c, \quad c = c0) \\ &\supseteq f_C(c) \cap f_C(c) \quad (\text{by Lemma 2.1}) \\ &= f_C(c) \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\xi_C \circ \xi_C \supset \xi_C \text{ and so } \xi_C \circ \xi_C = \xi_C.$$

□

6. Soft uni-product applied on soft parts of soft uni near-rings

Definition 6.1. Let N be a NR and ξ_N and ζ_N be soft sets over the common universe U . Then, *soft uni-product* $\xi_N * \zeta_N$ is defined by

$$(\xi_N * \zeta_N)(x) = \begin{cases} \bigcap_{x=yz} \{\xi_N(y) \cup \zeta_N(z)\}, & \text{if } \exists y, z \in N \text{ such that } x = yz, \\ \emptyset, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for all $x \in N$. It is obvious that if N is a NR with identity, then the second condition does not exist.

Theorem 6.1. Let N be a NR with identity, ξ_N be a SUN and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Then,

$$\xi_M * \xi_M \supset \xi_M.$$

Proof. Since N is a NR with identity, there exist elements $x, y \in M$ such that $m = xy$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_M * \xi_M)(m) &= \bigcap_{m=xy} \{\xi_M(x) \cup \xi_M(y)\} \\ &\supseteq \bigcap_{m=xy} \xi_M(xy) \\ &= \bigcap \xi_M(m) \\ &= \xi_M(m) \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\xi_M * \xi_M \supseteq \xi_M.$$

Here, since ξ_N is a SUN , $\xi_N(xy) \subseteq \xi_N(x) \cup \xi_N(y)$ for all $x \in N$. And, since ξ_M is the restricted function of f to M , then $\xi_M(xy) \subseteq \xi_M(x) \cup \xi_M(y)$. That is, ξ_M is a SUN , too. \square

Note that the converse, that is $\xi_M \supseteq \xi_M * \xi_M$ does not hold as seen in the following example.

Example 6.1. Let $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be the the (right) NR in Example 5.1. Assume that N is the set of parameters and $U = S_3$, symmetric group, is the universal set. We define a soft set ξ_N over U by

$$\xi_N(0) = \{(1)\}, \quad \xi_N(1) = \{(1), (12), (13)\}, \quad \xi_N(2) = \{(1), (12)\}, \quad \xi_N(3) = \{(1), (12), (13)\}$$

Then, one can easily show that the soft set ξ_N is a SUN over U and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_N$ by Theorem 3.1. Moreover, all x element of N , can be expressed as $x = yz$. Hence,

$$\xi_N * \xi_N \neq \emptyset.$$

However, it is seen that

$$(\xi_N * \xi_N)(2) = \{(1), (12), (13)\},$$

thus, $\xi_N \not\supseteq \xi_N * \xi_N$.

As is seen, $\xi_M * \xi_M$ needs not be equal to ξ_M , however we have the following :

Theorem 6.2. Let ξ_N be a SUN and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Then,

$$(\xi_M * \xi_M)(0) = \xi_M(0).$$

Proof. First note that, since $0 = 0 \cdot 0$, $(\xi_M * \xi_M)(0) \neq \emptyset$. Moreover,

$$(\xi_M * \xi_M)(0) \supseteq \xi_M(0)$$

is obvious by Theorem 6.1. Therefore, we need to show that

$$(\xi_M * \xi_M)(0) \subseteq \xi_M(0).$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_M * \xi_M)(0) &= \bigcap_{0=xy} \{\xi_M(x) \cup \xi_M(y)\} \\ &\subseteq \xi_M(0) \cup \xi_M(0) \\ &= \xi_M(0) \end{aligned}$$

the proof is completed. \square

It is known that if ξ_N is a *SUN*, then $\xi_N(0) \subseteq \xi_N(x)$ for all $x \in N$. Moreover, we have the following:

Theorem 6.3. *Let $N = N_0$, ξ_N be a *SUN* and $(\xi_N)_0 = \xi_M$. Then,*

$$(\xi_M * \xi_M)(0) \subseteq \xi_M(x)$$

for all $x \in M$.

Proof. Let $x, y \in M$ such that $0 = xy$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_M * \xi_M)(0) &= \bigcap_{0=xy} \{\xi_M(x) \cup \xi_M(y)\} \\ &\subseteq \xi_M(x) \cup \xi_M(0) \quad (\text{since } 0 = x0) \\ &\subseteq \xi_M(x) \cup \xi_M(x) \quad (\text{by Lemma 2.2}) \\ &= \xi_M(x) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the proof is completed. □

Theorem 6.4. *Let N be a *NR*, $N = N_c$ and ξ_N be a *SUN*. If $(\xi_N)_c = f_C$, then*

$$\xi_C * \xi_C = \xi_C.$$

Proof. Note that since $N = N_c$,

$$(\xi_C * \xi_C) \neq \emptyset.$$

Let $x, y \in C$ such that $c = xy$. It follows that,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_C * \xi_C)(c) &= \bigcap_{c=xy} \{f_C(x) \cup f_C(y)\} \\ &\supseteq \bigcap_{c=xy} f_C(xy) \\ &= \bigcap f_C(c) \\ &= f_C(c) \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\xi_C * \xi_C \supset \xi_C.$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_C * \xi_C)(c) &= \bigcap_{c=xy} \{\xi_C(x) \cup \xi_C(y)\} \\ &\subseteq \xi_C(c) \cup \xi_C(0) \quad (\text{since } N = N_c, \quad c = c0) \\ &\subseteq \xi_C(c) \cap \xi_C(c) \quad (\text{by Lemma 2.2}) \\ &= \xi_C(c) \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\xi_C * \xi_C \subset \xi_C \quad \text{and therefore, } \xi_C * \xi_C = \xi_C.$$

□

7. Conclusion

The concepts soft int near-rings and soft uni near-rings were first introduced and studied in [52] and [53]. In this paper, by using the soft sets, we have defined soft zero-symmetric part and soft constant part of soft int near-rings and soft uni near-rings. We have obtained many results on some operations of soft sets which preserve under soft zero-symmetric part and soft constant parts. Furthermore, we have defined soft int-product and soft uni-product of soft int near-ring and soft uni near-ring and have given some applications of them to soft parts of soft int near-rings and soft uni near-rings, respectively. The construction of the soft 0-symmetric part and the soft constant part aids in the advancement of the soft near-ring theory as the 0-symmetric and constant sections of a near-ring structure are crucial for characterizing the near-ring. To extend this study, one can further study the relations between zero-symmetric part (resp. constant part) of a near-ring and soft zero-symmetric part (resp. soft constant part) of a soft int(or uni) near-ring.

Acknowledgment

Authors equally contributed to this work.

References

- [1] Molodtsov D. Soft set theory-first results. *Comput Math Appl* 1999; 37: 19-31.
- [2] Acar U, Koyuncu F, Tanay B. Soft sets and soft rings. *Comput Math Appl* 2010; 59: 3458-3463.
- [3] Aktaş H, Çağman N. Soft sets and soft groups. *Inform Sci* 2007; 177: 2726-2735.
- [4] Sezgin A, Atagün AO. Soft groups and normalistic soft groups. *Comput Math Appl* 2011; 62 (2) : 685-698.
- [5] Feng F, Jun YB, Zhao X. Soft semirings. *Comput Math Appl* 2008; 56: 2621-2628.
- [6] Jun YB. Soft BCK/BCI-algebras. *Comput Math Appl* 2008; 56: 1408-1413.
- [7] Jun YB, Park CH. Applications of soft sets in ideal theory of BCK/BCI-algebras. *Inform Sci* 2008; 178: 2466-2475.
- [8] Jun YB, Lee KJ, Zhan J. Soft p -ideals of soft BCI-algebras. *Comput Math Appl* 2009; 58: 2060-2068.
- [9] Jun YB, Lee KJ, Park CH. Soft set theory applied to ideals in d -algebras. *Comput Math Appl* 2009; 57: 367-378.
- [10] KazancıO, Yılmaz Ş, Yamak S. Soft sets and soft BCH-algebras. *Hacet J Math Stat* 2010; 39 (2): 205-217.
- [11] Sezgin A, Atagün AO, Aygün E. A note on soft near-rings and idealistic soft near-rings. *Filomat* 2011; 25(1): 53-68.
- [12] Zhan J, Jun YB. Soft BL-algebras based on fuzzy sets. *Comput. Math. Appl* 2010; 59(6): 2037-2046.
- [13] Atagün AO, Sezgin A. Soft substructures of rings, fields and modules. *Comput Math Appl* 2011; 61(3): 592-601.
- [14] Sezgin A, Atagün AO, Çağman N. (2011) Union soft substructures of near-rings and N-groups. *Neural Comput Appl* 2011; 21 (1):133-143.
- [15] Mahmood T, Rehman ZU, Sezgin A. Lattice ordered soft near rings. *Korean Journal of Mathematics* 2018; 26 (3): 503-517.
- [16] Jana C, Pal M, Karaaslan F, Sezgin A. (α, β) -soft intersectional rings and ideals with their applications. *New Mathematics and Natural Computation* 2019; 15(2): 333-350.
- [17] Muştuoğlu E, Sezgin A, Türk, ZK. Some characterizations on soft uni-groups and normal soft uni-groups. *Journal of Computer Applications* 2016; 155 (10): 1-8.
- [18] Sezer AS, Çağman N, Atagün AO. Uni-soft substructures of groups. *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics* 2015; 9(2): 235-246.

- [19] Sezer AS. Certain Characterizations of LA-semigroups by soft sets. *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems* 2014; 27 (2): 1035-1046.
- [20] Özlü. Ş. Soft covered ideals in semigroups. *Acta Universitatis Sapientiae Mathematica* 2020; 12 (2): 317-346.
- [21] Sezgin A, Orbay M. Analysis of semigroups with soft intersection ideals, *Acta Universitatis Sapientiae Mathematica* 2022; 14 (1) 166-210.
- [22] Anitha N, Latha M. A study on T-Fuzzysoft subhemirings of a hemiring. *Asia Mathematica* 2017; 1 (1): 1-6.
- [23] Subha VS, Dhanalakshmi P. Characterization of near-ring by interval valued Picture fuzzy ideals. *Asia Mathematica* 2021; 5 (3): 14 – 21.
- [24] Özlü Ş. Generalized Dice measures of single valued neutrosophic type-2 hesitant fuzzy sets and their application to multi-criteria decision making problems. *Int. J. Mach. Learn. Cyber* (2023); 14: 33–62.
- [25] Özlü Ş. Multi-criteria decision making based on vector similarity measures of picture type-2 hesitant fuzzy sets. *Granul. Comput* 2023; 8: 1505–1531.
- [26] Özlü Ş. Interval Valued q- Rung Orthopair Hesitant Fuzzy Choquet Aggregating Operators in Multi-Criteria Decision Making Problems. *Gazi University Journal of Science Part C: Design and Technology* 2022; 2 10(4): 1006-1025.
- [27] Özlü Ş. Interval Valued Bipolar Fuzzy Prioritized Weighted Dombi Averaging Operator Based On Multi-Criteria Decision Making Problems. *Gazi University Journal of Science Part C: Design and Technology* 2022; 10(4); 841-857.
- [28] Maji PK, Biswas R, Roy AR. Soft set theory. *Comput Math Appl* 2003; 45: 555-562.
- [29] Ali MI, Feng F, Liu X, Min WK, Shabir M. On some new operations in soft set theory. *Comput Math Appl* 2009; 57: 1547-1553.
- [30] Sezgin A, Atagün AO. On operations of soft sets. *Comput Math Appl* 2011; 61(5): 1457-1467.
- [31] Babitha KV, Sunil JJ. Soft set relations and functions. *Comput Math Appl* 2010; 60(7): 1840-1849.
- [32] Majumdar P, Samanta SK. On soft mappings. *Comput Math Appl* 2010; 60(9): 2666-2672.
- [33] Feng F, Liu XY, Leoreanu-Fotea V, Jun YB. Soft sets and soft rough sets. *Inform Sci* 2011; 181(6): 1125-1137.
- [34] Feng F, Li C, Davvaz B, Ali MI. Soft sets combined with fuzzy sets and rough sets: a tentative approach. *Soft Comput* 2010; 14(6): 899-911.
- [35] Ali MI, Shabir M, Naz M. Algebraic structures of soft sets associated with new operations. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications* 2011; 61(9): 2647-2654.
- [36] Sezgin A, Ahmad S, Mehmood, A. A new operation on soft sets: Extended difference of soft sets. *Journal of New Theory* 2019; 27: 33-42.
- [37] Stojanovic, NS. A new operation on soft sets: Extended symmetric difference of soft sets. *Military Technical Courier* 2021; 69(4): 779-791.
- [38] Sezgin A, Atagün AO. New soft set operation: Complementary soft binary piecewise plus operation. *Matrix Science Mathematic* 2023; 7(2): 110-127.
- [39] Sezgin A, Aybek FN. New soft set operation: Complementary soft binary piecewise gamma operation. *Matrix Science Mathematic* 2023; 7(1): 27-45.
- [40] Sezgin A, Aybek FN, Atagün, AO. New soft set operation: Complementary soft binary piecewise intersection operation. *Black Sea Journal of Engineering and Science* 2023; 6(4): 330-346.
- [41] Sezgin A, Sezgin A, Aybek FN, Güngör NB. New soft set operation: Complementary soft binary piecewise union operation. *Acta Informatica Malaysia* 2023; (7)1: 38-53.
- [42] Sezgin A, Demirci AM. New soft set operation: complementary soft binary piecewise star operation. *Ikonion Journal of Mathematics* 2023; 5(2): 24-52.

- [43] Sezgin A, Yavuz E. New Soft Set Operation: Complementary Soft Binary Piecewise Lambda Operation. Sinop University Journal of Natural Sciences 8(2): 101-133.
- [44] Sezgin A, Yavuz E. A new soft set operation: Soft binary piecewise symmetric difference operation. Necmettin Erbakan University Journal of Science and Engineering 2023; 5(2): 150-168.
- [45] Sezgin A, Çağman N. New soft set operation: Complementary soft binary piecewise difference operation. Osmaniye Korkut Ata University Journal of the Institute of Science and Technology 2024; 7(1): 58-94.
- [46] Sezgin A, Çalışıcı H. A comprehensive study on soft binary piecewise difference operation. Eskişehir Technical University Journal of Science and Technology B-Theoretical Science 2024; 12(1): 32-54.
- [47] Çağman N, Enginoğlu S. Soft matrix theory and its decision making. Comput Math Appl 2010; 59: 3308-3314.
- [48] Çağman N, Enginoğlu S. Soft set theory and uni-int decision making. Eur J Oper Res 2010; 207: 848-855.
- [49] Maji PK, Roy AR, Biswas R. An application of soft sets in a decision making problem. Comput Math Appl 2002; 44: 1077-1083.
- [50] Manikantan T, Ramasamy P, Sezgin A. Soft Quasi-ideals of soft near-rings. Sigma J Eng Nat Sci 2023;41(3):565-574.
- [51] Molodtsov DA, Leonov VY, Kovkov DV. Soft sets technique and its application. Nechetkie Sistemy i Myagkie Vychisleniya 2006; 1(1): 8-39.
- [52] Sezgin A, Atagün AO, Çağman N. Soft intersection near-rings and its applications to near-ring theory, Neural Comput and Applic (2012); 21 (1): 221-229.
- [53] Sezgin A, Atagün AO, Çağman N, Demir H. On near-rings with soft union ideals and applications, New Mathematics and Natural Computation 2022; 18 (2): 495-511.
- [54] Pilz G. Near-rings. North Holland Publishing Company, Amsterdam-New York-Oxford, 1983.
- [55] Perumal R, Arulprakasam R, Radhakrishnan M. A Note on Normal Seminear-Rings 2017; 1 (2): 15-21.
- [56] Atagün AO, Groenewald NJ. Primeness in near-rings with multiplicative semi-groups satisfying the three identities. J Math Sci Adv Appl 2009; 2: 137-145.